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The Clustering System of the Cotton-Textile Industry in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is the Main Factor for the Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship

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***Abstract:** This article discusses the relevance of cluster system development in the agro-industrial complex. The history of the emergence of the term cluster and its role in the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in our country are studied. Also, factors affecting the situation and development of small business in the Republic of Karakalpakstan are analyzed.*

***Key words:** regional economy clustering, small business, regional state support, agriculture.*

In the modern economy, the importance of small business and entrepreneurship is steadily increasing. The unique flexibility of small business, the simplicity and low cost of management, the ability to stimulate scientific and technical development, accelerate the implementation of its achievements, and mobilize the important financial and production resources of society determine its important economic role.

A great attention to the development of entrepreneurship in our country can be seen from the fact that the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, has become a tradition every year in August, on the eve of Entrepreneurs' Day, the meeting of the President with the aim of solving issues together in the form of an open dialogue with entrepreneurs has become a tradition.

The implementation of such measures and reforms shows that the role of small business and entrepreneurship in the country's economy is very important. We can see this in the table below of the share of small business entities in GDP. (Table 1)

Analyzing Table 1, by the end of 2022, the share of small business in the Republic's gross domestic product (GDP) was 51.8 percent. In terms of regions, the largest share was observed in Jizzakh (78.4 percent of the gross added value created in the region), Surkhandarya (76.8 percent) and Bukhara (74.1 percent) regions.

Table 1. The share of small business entities in the total GDP of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Territory	2019 year	2020 year	2021 year	2022 year	2023 year
Republic of Uzbekistan	56,0	54,8	54,1	51,8	51,2
Republic of Karakalpakstan	56,3	58,3	56,3	56,6	58,7
Andijan region	69,6	70,1	72,2	69,5	66,0
Bukhara region	74,3	75,7	75,9	74,1	71,7
Jizzakh region	83,1	83,0	80,1	78,4	73,7
Qashqadaryo region	70,8	71,6	69,9	68,1	68,4
Navoiy region	30,7	25,7	27,1	26,8	26,0
Namangan region	75,9	74,7	73,8	72,8	72,8
Samarqand region	75,2	74,3	74,1	71,4	72,8
Surxondaryo region	78,8	77,2	77,0	76,8	75,9
Sirdaryo region	69,8	70,7	69,1	65,4	63,6
Toshkent region	51,3	49,5	45,6	46,5	48,7
Farg'ona region	69,3	70,7	69,8	68,9	69,5
Xorazm region	76,4	76,2	73,7	71,6	69,7
Tashkent city	53,1	51,5	48,8	46,8	49,8

Source: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The smallest share of small businesses was recorded in Navoi region (26.8%). If we look at the indicators from 2019 to 2023, we can observe a decreasing trend in all regions. It is no exaggeration to cite the economic downturn caused by the Covid-19 pandemic as the first reason for this.

From the above table, we can see that in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the role of small business entities in the economic development of the region is not insignificant. This indicator increased from 56.6 to 58.7 (by 3.71%) in 2023 compared to 2022. From this we can conclude that the number of small enterprises in the region is increasing and their production volume is increasing.

The Republic of Karakalpakstan, the largest region of Uzbekistan, covers an area of 166,600 km², which is almost 40% of the Republic's land area.

The territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan consists of 16 districts, 12 cities and 146 villages. (Table 2) Kongirot district with an area of 76,000 is considered the largest district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and Takhiatash district with 180 is the smallest. The largest gatherings of rural citizens are located in Amudarya and Tortkol districts.

Table 2. The size of the main indicators of small business and private entrepreneurship in the economic sectors of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Years	2019-y	2020-y	2021-y	2022-y	2023-y
Industry (billion soums)	2 517,5	3 382,1	3 721,8	3 744,6	5 330,2
Construction (billion soums)	2 943,5	3 495,1	4 168,9	4 765,3	5 381,2

soums)					
Trade (billion soums)	5 005,9	5 947,3	7 760,3	10 038,3	10 955,6
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries (billion soums)	8 660,7	10 056,7	11 740,2	13 502,6	15 530,8
Services (billion soums)	3 037,8	3 347,4	4 410,3	5 204,2	6 613,9
Export (million US dollars)	88,4	78,8	92,4	68,9	93,6
Import (million US dollars)	190,1	125,3	140,0	109,8	117,9

Source: Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Statistics Department of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

We can see from the table that by the end of 2023, the largest production volume of the agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector was equal to 15,530.8 billion soums. This means an increase of 15% compared to 2022. The share of small business entities in the export also increased by 30% in 2023 compared to 2022 and amounted to 93.6 million US dollars.

In terms of the level of development of small business and private entrepreneurship, the Republic of Karakalpakstan was ranked among the moderately developed regions of Uzbekistan (seventh place). In 2023, the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the gross territorial product of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was 58.7 percent (51.2 percent on average for the republic).

In the economy of Nukus city, Takhtakopir, Qonlikol and Ellikkala districts, small business and private entrepreneurship occupy an important place. This sector occupies a relatively small place in the economy of Takhyatosh city, Moynaq, Kungirov, Tortkol and Khojaly districts. It should be noted that in regions where the share of large-scale industrial production does not exist or is small, the share of small businesses is greater.

The main branches of agriculture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are grain growing (wheat and rice raw materials), cotton growing, cattle breeding and silk growing. In 2023, 266,396 tons of raw cotton were grown in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. (Table 4)

Analyzing the table, we can see that cotton is not grown at all in Moynaq and Bozatov districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In 2023, the volume of cotton production increased by 11.3% compared to last year and amounted to 266,396 tons. In this regard, Amudarya District is the first place, growing 48,086 tons of cotton. The lowest indicators in the region are observed in the cities of Takhiatash and Nukus.

In 2017, 92,100 hectares of land were allocated for cotton cultivation in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, but by 2023, this indicator decreased by 6% and made 86,800.2 hectares of land. Despite this, the volume of cotton harvest increased by 38%. This is due to the increase in the productivity of the land.

The rapid development of the cotton industry in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is the result of the socio-economic reforms carried out in the region.

We can include the cotton-textile clusters that are being organized in our country to such reforms. The first cluster was established in the Republic of Karakalpakstan in 2018. Currently, 14 cotton-textile clusters are operating in the region.

Conclusions.

It is possible to distinguish the advantages of the cluster approach not only in achieving the strategic goals of the regions, but also in supporting small business and entrepreneurship.

1. A cluster of small enterprises is more resistant to the negative effects of the environment, has a longer life and is better protected from risks. Therefore, supporting a cluster significantly reduces the risk of wasting limited resources compared to supporting an individual small business. Small sole proprietorships can come and go quickly. However, world experience shows that clusters are a more stable entity.

2. Due to limited resources, powers, and decision-making horizons, individual small businesses are rarely able to significantly influence the economic landscape of a region or large municipality.

3. Cluster support allows to minimize or eliminate limitations in the activity of small enterprises related to financial, human, organizational resources and personnel competencies. Within the framework of the traditional approach, it is necessary to provide financing, advice and organizational support to individual enterprises.

The formation of clusters of small enterprises significantly increases the efficiency of small business support, reduces restrictions and risks to this type of activity, and also regulates its development in accordance with its strategic vision and goals.

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